

Design and evaluation of electrospun fibers for unidirectional buccal delivery of atorvastatin

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Abstract

This study focused on atorvastatin calcium trihydrate (ATV), which is characterized by low bioavailability due to high intestinal metabolism and the hepatic first-pass effect. The buccal route is suitable for addressing ATV-related issues and aids in diminishing swallowing difficulties in older adults, the primary beneficiaries. The novelty of this work lies in the use of the electrospinning technique to produce ATV-loaded electrospun fibers, aiming to stabilize the drug in an amorphous form to enhance its dissolution in saliva and to incorporate it into a unidirectional tablet to control drug release in a single direction. ATV fibers were prepared using polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP) with various co-solvents (propylene glycol, glycerin, Tween 80) and ethanol concentrations. The selected electrospun fibers formulated with a high amount of ethanol (F8) demonstrated 93.9% drug release, a disintegration time of 3 min, and nanosized fibers and were chosen for tablet preparations. The batches exhibited adequate mucoadhesion, and their drug release within 4 hours was 25.5%, 83.27%, 70.27%, and 100% for batches B1, B2, B3, and B4, respectively. The most prominent factor affecting the release rate was the addition of 7.5 mg of the super-disintegrant croscarmellose sodium. Permeation studies showed that 68.27% of ATV permeated through B4 over 24 hours, indicating that electrospun ATV-loaded PVP fibers can be efficiently formulated into mucoadhesive buccal tablets with rapid disintegration, drug release, and effective permeation, suggesting a strong prospect for buccal tablets in populations with swallowing difficulties.

Keywords

atorvastatin calcium trihydrate, electrospinning, fibers, swallowing difficulties, unidirectional buccal tablet

Introduction

Swallowing difficulties constitute a significant issue for older adults, resulting in substantial obstacles to effective medication management, therapy delivery, and sufficient nutrition (Kelly et al. 2009). Considering these challenges is crucial for enhancing the quality of life of older people. Hence, alternative routes, such as oral cavity delivery, can resolve this issue due to the ease of administration and

effectiveness in drug provision (El-Samaligy et al. 2006). The oral cavity is widely suitable for both local and systemic applications (Nair et al. 2023), such as buccal delivery, for which several commercially available dosage forms have been developed, including tablets, gels, and patches (Montero-Padilla et al. 2017).

Buccal delivery refers to the transport of drugs through the mucosal membranes lining the cheeks, enabling direct absorption into the systemic circulation. The drug core

in this work was atorvastatin (ATV) in its calcium trihydrate form, which, according to the biopharmaceutical classification system, is classified as a Class II drug. ATV effectively reduces cholesterol and triglyceride levels in patients with hyperlipidemia and cardiovascular disease (Dinakaran et al. 2013). ATV is known for its low oral bioavailability of only 14%, with one of the main issues being presystemic clearance in the gastrointestinal mucosa, in addition to the first-pass effect (Lennernäs 2003). Thus, the characteristics of the buccal route make ATV an ideal candidate for buccal administration to bypass these issues, which aligns with the prerequisites for buccal drug administration (Hua 2019). This study focused on the electrospinning technique to create fibers loaded with ATV, thereby increasing the potential for a stable amorphous drug within the fabricated mat of electrospun fibers and ensuring the dissolution of ATV in saliva, which aids in better absorption through the buccal mucosa or into the gastrointestinal tract upon swallowing (Lopez et al. 2014). It is well known that the electrospinning technique generates fibers by subjecting a droplet of a viscous polymer solution to a high voltage, which overcomes its surface tension. This process causes the solvent to evaporate, resulting in a fibrous mat that converts drugs into an amorphous state (Tawfik et al. 2021). Electrospun fibers possess a significant surface-area-to-volume ratio, high porosity, and a substantial drug-loading capacity.

This study was motivated by prior findings that highlighted the potential of buccal delivery for atorvastatin. To the best of our knowledge, no prior work has employed the electrospinning technique to prepare fibers loaded with atorvastatin for the solid buccal dosage form. Additionally, the electrospun fibers were prepared using co-solvents, including Tween, propylene glycol (PG), and glycerin, as no previous study had explored this approach with polyvinylpyrrolidone. Considering the swallowing issues of older people, this study aimed to develop mucoadhesive buccal tablets containing ATV loaded within electrospun fibers to ensure the consistent solubility of ATV. Additionally, this study examined the effect of the addition of the super-disintegrant croscarmellose sodium to the mucoadhesive buccal tablet formulations on the ATV release duration.

Materials and methods

Materials

Atorvastatin calcium trihydrate (ATV) was acquired from Energy Chemical in China; croscarmellose sodium was obtained from Shanghai Ruizheng Chemical Technology Co., Ltd., China. Ethanol (99%) was sourced from Honeywell in Germany. Carbomer 934, ethyl cellulose (EC), hydroxypropyl methylcellulose K4M (HPMC), mannitol, and magnesium stearate (MS) were all procured from Macklin in China. Lactose was obtained from Alpha Chemica, India. Glycerin (GL) was obtained from Nacalai Tesque Co. in Kyoto, Japan, and microcrystalline cellulose

(MCC) was sourced from Changsha Goomo Chemical Technology in China. Propylene glycol was purchased from PanReac Química SLU in Spain, and polyvinylpyrrolidone K90 (PVP), Tween 80, and sodium alginate were obtained from Glentham Life Sciences in the UK, Merck in Germany, and Alpha Chemica in India, respectively.

Methods

Preparation of electrospinning solution

The drug-spinning solution was prepared by dissolving PVP in ethanol and stirring it at ambient temperature for at least 60 minutes using a magnetic stirrer until it was fully dissolved. ATV was then added to the polymer solution with continuous stirring for an additional 60 minutes to achieve a homogeneous solution (Alshaya et al. 2022), as illustrated in Fig. 1. The spinning formulations were divided into three groups, as outlined in Table 1.

Determination of electrospinning solution viscosity

Before applying the electrospinning process, the viscosity of the polymeric solutions was assessed using a viscometer (63s spindle) at room temperature and different rotation speeds (20, 30, 50, 60, and 100 rpm).

Electrospinning process to prepare electrospun fibers

The electrospinning process setup included a high-voltage direct current power supply generator capable of reaching a maximum voltage of 10 kV. The drug-polymer solutions were dispensed into 10 mL disposable syringes equipped with 22G tip-ground-to-flat needles mounted on a horizontally positioned syringe pump. The resulting fibers were deposited onto aluminium foil wrapped around a rotating drum collector, as shown in Fig. 1, which rotated at a speed of 200 rpm. The ambient temperature and relative humidity were maintained at 25 ± 2 °C and 35 ± 1 %, respectively. The distance between the needle and collector was 12 cm, and the flow rate was 1 mL/min.

Characterization of spinning fibers

Physical appearance of fibers

The physical assessment of all formulations was visual, achieved by monitoring the accumulation of collector fibers.

Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy and differential scanning calorimetry

Two hundred milligrams of potassium bromide, ATV, PVP, ATV fibers, and co-solvents were mixed and compressed into disks for FTIR analysis (Shimadzu 8400S, Japan).

For DSC analysis (DSC 131 Evo, Setaram, France), aluminium pans contained 2–5 mg samples that were heated from 21 °C to 280 °C at 1.5 °C/min under a 50 mL/min nitrogen flow (Vuddanda et al. 2016).

Figure 1. Schematic illustration of the preparation of electrospinning solutions and fibers.

Table 1. Electrospinning solutions composition.

Content	Formulation No.							
	Group 1			Group 2			Group 3	
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8
Drug-to-polymer ratio	1:2	1:3	1:4	1:4	1:4	1:4	1:4	1:4
Polyvinyl pyrrolidone K90 (gm)	1	1.5	2	2	2	2	2	2
Tween 80 (mL)	–	–	–	0.5	–	–	–	–
PG (mL)	–	–	–	–	0.5	–	–	–
Glycerine (mL)	–	–	–	–	–	0.5	–	–
Ethanol (mL) up to	25	25	25	25	25	25	50	75

* ATV was 500 mg in each formulation.

Determination of drug loading (DL%), entrapment efficiency (EE%), and fiber yield (Y) of the drug-loaded fibers

ATV encapsulated within the fibers was assessed by dissolving the electrospun fibers, equivalent to 20 mg of atorvastatin acid, in 10 mL of 99% ethanol (Karthikeyan et al. 2012). The drug content was evaluated at λ_{max} 247 nm using a UV spectrophotometer, employing a pre-established, validated calibration curve equation ($y = 0.0226x - 0.0059$) in ethanol, with a correlation coefficient ($R^2 = 0.9979$). Drug loading and entrapment efficiency were calculated using Equations 1 and 2, respectively (Reda et al. 2017):

$$DL\% = \frac{\text{weight of the drug in fibers}}{\text{Weight of fibers}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

$$EE\% = \frac{\text{Weight of the drug in fibers}}{\text{Theoretical weight of the drug in fibers}} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

The yield (Y) of the fibers was also measured using Equation 3 (Alshaya et al. 2022):

$$Y\% = \frac{\text{The actual amount of fibers}}{\text{The theoretical amount of the fibers}} \times 100 \quad (3)$$

All studies were applied in triplicate.

Disintegration time of fibers

The disintegration time of drug-loaded fibers was evaluated using a modified version of the Petri dish assay, as described by (Tawfik et al. 2021). A time monitoring experiment was conducted using 3 mg of each fiber formulation in a Petri dish containing 10 mL of pre-warmed phosphate buffer (pH 6.8) at 37 °C, with gentle shaking in a water bath until complete disintegration of the fibers occurred.

In vitro release of fibers

In vitro release of fibers, equivalent to 20 mg of ATV, was studied in 900 mL phosphate buffer (pH 6.8) using a dissolution basket apparatus (Vanguard, USA) set at 37 ± 0.5 °C at 100 rpm for 4 hours (Boyapally et al. 2010). At each interval (5, 10, 15, 30, 60, 90, 120, 150, 180, and 240 minutes), 5 mL samples were taken and replaced with fresh buffer. Absorbance was read at 241 nm using a UV spectrophotometer with a standard calibration equation ($y = 0.01x - 0.0261$, $R^2 = 0.9974$).

Scanning electron microscopy

The fiber morphology and diameter were examined using a scanning electron microscope (Axia, ChemiSEM-Ther-

mo Scientific, USA). Before examination, the samples were gold sputter-coated under argon to enhance electrical conductivity. Images were captured by the XT microscope control software at an excitation voltage of 30 kV. The average fiber size was determined by measuring the diameters of the fibers in SEM images (Illangakoon et al. 2014).

Preparation of unidirectional buccal tablet

The unidirectional buccal tablet was created using the direct compression method. The fibers, equivalent to 20 mg of ATV, and the excipients were weighed individually as outlined in Table 2. All the ingredients were mixed, excluding ethyl cellulose.

Table 2. Mucoadhesive buccal tablet formulations.

Ingredients	B1	B2	B3	B4
HPMC K4M (mg)	30	10	10	10
Lactose (mg)	–	27	17	64.5
Mannitol (mg)	47	–	–	–
Microcrystalline cellulose (mg)	20	–	–	–
Sodium Alginate (mg)	–	50	60	15
Croscarmellose sodium (mg)	–	10	10	7.5
Total weight (mg)	200	200	200	200

** Fifty milligrams of fibers were added to all batches, equivalent to 20 mg of atorvastatin acid. In addition, 3 mg of magnesium stearate and 50 mg of ethyl cellulose were added to all batches.

The core tablets were formed using an 8 mm diameter single-punch tablet machine (RIVA MINIPRESS MII tablet machine) with manual operation. Ethyl cellulose was used as a backing layer (covering the tablet from three sides to ensure unidirectional release) and was filled into a round die with a 10 mm diameter on the tablet machine. The core tablet was then placed in the center above the ethyl cellulose and compressed to create the unidirectional buccal tablet (Koradia and Chaudhari 2018). The following excipients – HPMC, lactose or mannitol, microcrystalline cellulose or sodium alginate, croscarmellose sodium, and magnesium stearate – acted as mucoadhesive polymers, fillers, binders, super-disintegrants, and lubricants, respectively.

Characterization of mucoadhesive unidirectional buccal tablet

Physical appearance

The visual characteristics of the buccal tablet were observed following direct compression.

Weight variation, thickness with hardness, and surface pH

To conduct the weight variation test, three tablets of each formulation were weighed to determine their average weight. A digital vernier caliper (Mitutoyo Corporation, Japan) and an electronic hardness tester (YD-1, China) were used to measure the tablet thickness and hardness, respectively (Prasanna et al. 2011).

For surface pH measurement, the tablet was immersed in 10 mL of phosphate buffer solution (pH 6.8) for 2 hours at room temperature. Then, the electrode was brought into contact with the tablet surface and stabilized for 1 minute (He and Mu 2023).

Swelling percent

To assess the swelling percent, tablets were initially weighed and then attached to a glass slide, which was immersed in 10 mL of buffer (pH 6.8) at 37 ± 0.5 °C (Shanker et al. 2009). At 1, 2, 4, 6, and 8 hours, the tablets were removed, excess buffer was eliminated, and then they were accurately reweighed. The swelling percent was calculated using Equation 4 (Sogias et al. 2012).

$$SI = \frac{W_t - W_0}{W_0} * 100 \quad (4)$$

“ W_t ” corresponds to the weight at a particular time, and “ W_0 ” is the initial weight of the tablet. All experiments were conducted in triplicate to ensure consistency and reliability.

Mucoadhesion strength

The mucoadhesion strength was determined using a modified balance (Ali et al. 2002). Fresh sheep buccal mucosa was washed with phosphate buffer (pH 6.8) and fixed to a glass slide. A tablet was attached to another slide with adhesive. A beaker was placed on the opposite side of the balance and filled with water until the tablet detached. The required weight indicated bioadhesive strength. The test was repeated three times (Prasanna et al. 2011).

Disintegration time

Buccal tablet examinations were performed without any backing material. Three tablets from each batch were selected and placed in disintegration apparatus baskets (Karl Kolb, Germany). The disintegration process was carried out with continuous monitoring for 4 hours. Subsequently, the basket was removed from the solution to confirm the full disintegration of the tablets. All experiments were performed in triplicate (Shanker et al. 2009).

In vitro release of buccal tablet

Tablet formulations underwent a release study using a USP paddle apparatus (Vanguard, USA) with 500 mL of phosphate buffer (pH 6.8) at 50 rpm and 37 ± 0.5 °C. Tablets were glued with adhesive to a glass slide and positioned at the bottom of the vessel. At set intervals (5, 10, 15, 30, 60, 90, 120, 150, 180, and 240 minutes), 5 mL samples were taken, filtered through a 0.45 µm syringe filter, replaced with fresh medium, and analyzed at 241 nm by UV spectrophotometry (Shimadzu, Japan) (Shanker et al. 2009). The test was repeated three times.

Ex vivo permeation test

The permeation of ATV through sheep buccal mucosa was studied using Franz diffusion cells. Fresh sheep buccal mucosa, obtained from a slaughterhouse, was used for the experiments. Before testing, the tissue was kept in phosphate buffer (pH 6.8). The soaking buffer was read at 241 nm, the λ_{max} of ATV, as the soaking buffer solution was continuously changed and read by UV until zero absorbance was achieved to avoid interference from the tissue. The mucosa was cut into circular shapes and placed between the donor and receptor compartments. The buccal tablet was placed on the mucosa with the core side facing up, and both compartments were gently secured together (Prasanna et al. 2011). The receptor compartment was filled with 50 mL phosphate buffer (pH 6.8) at a stirring rate of 50 rpm and 37 ± 0.2 °C. A 5 mL sample was withdrawn at specified time intervals (1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 8, 12, 16, and 24 hours), replaced with the same volume, and analyzed by UV spectrophotometry at 241 nm. The flux of ATV was calculated using the cumulative amount of drug that permeated through 1.76 cm² of surface area over time, followed by determining the slope of the steady state.

Statistical analysis

A one-way ANOVA test was performed for statistical analysis of the in vitro release profiles of group 1 and group 2 fiber formulations, buccal tablets, and the swelling percentage of the four buccal tablet formulations. A t-test was applied for the in vitro release analysis of the group 3 fiber formulation.

Results

Determination of electrospinning solution viscosity

The viscosities of prepared solutions, as listed in Table 3, exhibited sufficient viscosity to be pumped into the syringe of the electrospinning apparatus, as higher amounts of PVP in the spinning solution led to increased viscosity.

Characterization of spinning fibers

Physical appearance of fibers

All formulations displayed a fiber mat deposited onto the aluminum foil on the device collector after being placed in the desiccator to ensure good storage conditions. The visual and tactile characteristics of the ATV-loaded fibers resembled those of disposable tissue.

Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) and differential scanning calorimetry

As depicted in Fig. 2A–C, the ATV spectrogram displayed prominent peaks at 3362 cm⁻¹, 3230 cm⁻¹, and 1650 cm⁻¹, corresponding to the stretching of N–H,

Table 3. Viscosity data of electrospinning solutions.

Formulations	Viscosity (cp)				
	100 rpm	60 rpm	50 rpm	30 rpm	20 rpm
F1	169	298	348	404	622
F2	173	305	357	483	685
F3	279	311	375	564	822
F4	288	355	412	575	827
F5	290	367	420	582	835
F6	296	378	432	590	841
F7	175	275	325	442	529
F8	125	193	307	407	506

O–H, and C=O groups, respectively. The PVP spectrogram displayed a prominent peak at 1650 cm⁻¹, which correlated with the C=O group, and a clear broad peak associated with the hydroxyl group between 3200 cm⁻¹ and 3600 cm⁻¹ (Rahma et al. 2016). Fig. 2A also presents the spectrograms of F1, F2, and F3 (Group 1). There was a clear shift in the F2 and F3 spectrograms from 1650 cm⁻¹ to 1666 cm⁻¹ and 1660 cm⁻¹, respectively. In addition, all F1, F2, and F3 exhibited the disappearance of the 3362 cm⁻¹ N–H-related peak in ATV, which suggests that the hydroxyl group of PVP might be overlaying it. Furthermore, Fig. 2B clarifies the spectrograms of Group 2 formulations (F4, F5, and F6), all of which demonstrated a persistent shift from 1650 cm⁻¹ to 1663 cm⁻¹, 1663 cm⁻¹, and 1667 cm⁻¹, respectively. Finally, Group 3 (F7 and F8) spectrograms consistently showed a shift in the carbonyl region from 1650 cm⁻¹ to 1674 cm⁻¹ and 1671 cm⁻¹, respectively. Groups 2 and 3 resembled Group 1 regarding the N–H peak at 3362 cm⁻¹.

DSC thermograms are illustrated in Fig. 2D–F. All formulations lacked the ATV melting peak at 169 °C and displayed only a peak near the transition temperature of PVP at 90 °C.

Determination of drug loading (DL%), entrapment efficiency (EE%), and fiber yield (Y%) of the drug-loaded fibers

Table 4 shows DL% and EE%. As the amount of polymer in the fiber formulations increased, the DL% decreased, while the EE% increased. Moreover, all formulations demonstrated a high Y%.

Disintegration time of fibers

The disintegration apparatus often used can replicate the volume and peristaltic movement of the gastrointestinal tract, but it does not effectively imitate the conditions of the oral cavity (Vuddanda et al. 2016). Therefore, the Petri dish method was utilized to determine the disintegration time of fibers. Fig. 3A, which shows F8 selected randomly, demonstrated that the subsequent disintegration continued until the fibers completely disappeared, which took approximately 3 minutes.

As illustrated in Table 4, the disintegration time results outline the duration until all electrospun fibers were completely disintegrated.

Figure 2. FTIR spectrograms within wavenumber ranges (400–4000 cm^{-1}) as A–C., presenting Groups 1, 2, and 3 of the fiber formulations. DSC thermograms with heating temperatures from 21 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ to 300 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ at a heating rate of 1.5 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, as shown in D–F., referring to Groups 1, 2, and 3 of the fiber formulations.

In vitro release of fibers

The release pattern of ATV from fiber formulations is displayed in Fig. 3B. Group 1 (F1, F2, and F3) demonstrated the percentage of release at 150 minutes, which was 70.5%, 80.4%, and 86.4%, respectively.

In Group 2 (F4, F5, and F6), the variation was due to the addition of the co-solvent. Specifically, F5, which

contains PG, exhibited a 95.59% release after 60 minutes, whereas F4 and F6, whose co-solvents were Tween 80 and glycerin, respectively, reached only 58.84% and 70.47%.

In the third group, the quantities of ATV and PVP remained constant, but the volume of ethanol was increased during the preparation of the spinning solution. F8 achieved a high release of 93.9% after 30 minutes, whereas F7 only reached 54.34%. The one-way ANOVA

Figure 3. A. Dissolution of ATV-loaded fibers by the Petri dish method and B. in vitro release of ATV-loaded fibers at 37 °C in 900 mL phosphate buffer (pH 6.8), (n = 3), ±SD.

Table 4. Drug loading, entrapment efficiency, yield, and disintegration time of ATV-loaded fibers.

Number of formulas	DL% ± SD	EE% ± SD	Yield%	Disintegration time (minutes)
F1	32.35 ± 0.44	97.07 ± 1.32	81.76 ± 1.66	3.5
F2	24.45 ± 0.54	97.81 ± 2.18	82.5 ± 1	3.7
F3	19.47 ± 0.53	97.37 ± 2.6	87.83 ± 1.52	4
F4	19.79 ± 0.35	98.99 ± 1.78	91.5 ± 1	3.2
F5	19.71 ± 0.18	98.55 ± 0.92	86.3 ± 1.25	3.3
F6	19.79 ± 0.53	98.99 ± 2.66	82.16 ± 1.04	4
F7	19.91 ± 0.18	99.58 ± 0.92	88.66 ± 1.52	3.2
F8	20.35 ± 0.13	101.7 ± 0.67	90.56 ± 1.35	3

test revealed no significant ($p > 0.05$) difference between the fiber formulations of Groups 1 and 2. In contrast, for Group 3, the paired t-test showed a significant difference between F7 and F8 since the p-value was < 0.05 .

Scanning electron microscopy

Three selected formulations, F3, F5, and F8, are illustrated in Fig. 4. The results are presented in two parts. The first part shows images scaled against 5 μm and 10 μm , providing very high magnification to reveal fiber diameter. The second part is scaled against 10, 50, and 100 μm to view the whole morphology. The nanosized fibers ranged from 134.9 to 821.9 nm in F3 and F8. In contrast, F5 exhibited fiber diameters ranging from 1.050 to 1.630 μm , with only a few fibers displaying nanosized characteristics.

Characterization of mucoadhesive uni-directional buccal tablet

Physical appearance

The tablet's physical appearance, as presented in Fig. 5A, shows that it is composed of two layers. The core layer

contained ATV and excipients, while the backing layer consisted of ethyl cellulose, which is water-insoluble, improving release in one direction.

Weight variation, thickness with hardness, and surface pH

All results are presented in Table 5. The weight variation of the tablet formulations was 199–200 mg \pm 0.577–1. Additionally, the hardness ranged from 3.93 to 4.32 kg/cm² \pm 0.028–0.095, while thickness varied from 3.33 to 3.46 mm \pm 0.005–0.015. The surface pH of the tablet formulations ranged from 6.4 to 6.9.

Swelling percent

As shown in Fig. 5B, B1 showed a swelling percentage of 103%. In B2, B3, and B4, SI reached 128.2%, 132.5%, and 117%, respectively. The one-way ANOVA test revealed no significant ($p > 0.05$) difference between any of the formulations.

Mucoadhesive strength

The mucoadhesive strength of the buccal tablets, as shown in Table 5, was consistent across all batches (B1, B2, B3, and B4).

Figure 4. SEM images of ATV-loaded fibers. **A.** Fiber diameters, and **B.** micrographs under different magnifications scaled at 10, 50, and 100 μm. The first row represents the micrographs of F3, while the second and third rows represent F5 and F8, respectively.

Table 5. Buccal tablet physicochemical properties.

No. of formulation	Weight variation (Mg) ± SD	Hardness (Kg/cm ²) ± SD	Thickness (mm) ± SD	Surface pH ± SD	Mucoadhesive strength (gm) ± SD	Disintegration time (minutes) ± SD
B1	200 ± 1	4.32 ± 0.030	3.33 ± 0.012	6.4 ± 0.1	28.63 ± 0.305	54 ± 1
B2	199 ± 1	4.08 ± 0.028	3.46 ± 0.005	6.903 ± 0.047	27.13 ± 0.07	43 ± 1
B3	200 ± 1	4.10 ± 0.095	3.42 ± 0.01	6.903 ± 0.047	27.85 ± 0.050	52 ± 1
B4	199.66 ± 0.577	3.93 ± 0.057	3.38 ± 0.015	6.903 ± 0.047	24.195 ± 0.006	42 ± 1

Disintegration time

The disintegration time of tablet formulations, as presented in Table 5, ranged from 42 to 52 minutes, which is considered acceptable and less than 4 hours. This value closely matches that of the tizanidine hydrochloride buccal tablet prepared with HPMC K4M (Shanker et al. 2009).

In vitro release

According to the release profiles shown in Fig. 5C, B4 exhibited around 100% ATV release after 3 hours, while B2 and B3 reached 83% and 70%, respectively, after 4 hours. B1 was the slowest tablet to release ATV, with a release of 25% after 4 hours. The one-way ANOVA test demonstrated a very significant difference only between B1 and B4 ($p < 0.01$). All other pairwise comparisons showed no significant differences ($p > 0.05$).

Ex vivo permeation test

B4 was selected for the permeation study, as it yielded a higher release percentage of ATV from its dosage form. The permeation percentages were 57.1%, 58.5%, and 68.27% at 12, 16, and 24 hours, respectively, as illustrated in Fig. 5D. The calculated flux was 1.34 mg/cm²/hr.

Discussion

This work aimed to formulate ATV as electrospun fibers loaded in buccal tablets to assist geriatric individuals with swallowing difficulties, since ATV undergoes presystemic metabolism.

The unidirectional buccal tablet was preferred to ensure controlled release towards the mucosa, whereas the

Figure 5. A. Physical appearance of the buccal tablet, showing the core and the backing layer. B. Swelling percent of the four batches in phosphate buffer (pH 6.8). C. Dissolution of B1, B2, B3, and B4 in 500 mL phosphate buffer (pH 6.8). D. Ex vivo ATV permeation through sheep mucosa. (n = 3), \pm SD.

plain buccal tablet allowed drug release from multiple directions, resulting in more drug being swallowed into the stomach and a high possibility of drug concentration fluctuation in plasma rather than permeating through the mucosa (El-Nabarawi et al. 2016).

In previous studies, ATV was developed as a bilayer tablet using various ratios of Carbopol 934, acacia, and HPMC K-15 to prolong or control the release of ATV from the tablet core (Asha John et al. 2010). Additionally, ATV was formulated as a microemulsion contained in a buccal hydroxypropyl methylcellulose film to ensure its solubility within a thermodynamically stable system (Soliman et al. 2021).

This discussion section begins with the results of the evaluation of prepared electrospun fibers, followed by buccal tablet formulations.

The three groups of ATV-electrospinning solutions were first tested for their viscosities, as shown in Table 3, and how PVP and its ratio affect the solution intended for injection into the electrospinning process pump. The higher PVP amount in the spinning solution increased viscosity, which was also reflected in nifedipine spinning solutions prepared with increasing amounts of Eudragit, resulting in increased viscosity (da Costa et al. 2015). In addition, adding co-solvents to the solutions enhanced

viscosity, whereas increasing the volume of ethanol in the third group decreased viscosity. The viscosities of all varied electrospinning solutions did not hinder the electrospinning process, and the obtained electrospun fibers were further investigated.

FTIR was the first study to test the possible interaction among the contents of the formulations (Çelik 2017), as shown in Fig. 2A–C. The shift from the original peaks of pure materials indicated a high probability of the carbonyl groups, whether belonging to ATV or PVP, in hydrogen bonding. However, the shift was not present in the F1 spectrogram, which could be attributed to the small impact of the low amount of PVP in F1. The same trend was observed in the spectrograms of Groups 2 and 3. It is believed that ethanol, as a solvent, evaporated during the spinning process without disregarding its impact on increasing the hydrogen bonding opportunities between PVP and ATV, both of which are soluble in ethanol. In summary, FTIR analysis confirmed that all formulations exhibited hydrogen bonding between ATV and polymers, which aided in stabilizing the amorphous state of ATV within the fabricated fibers.

In addition, DSC is crucial for detecting thermal transitions in electrospun fibers, and the disappearance of the

ATV melting peak suggests that the ATV was in an amorphous state, integrated into the fabrication of the electrospun fibers. In a separate study, indomethacin and griseofulvin also demonstrated an amorphous state following the formulation of electrospun fibers using PVP polymers (Lopez et al. 2014).

The FTIR and DSC analyses were aligned, revealing changes that confirmed the likelihood of hydrogen bonding between ATV and polymers, thereby ensuring the amorphous nature of the fibers.

The three groups of electrospun fiber formulations were further studied by applying DL%, EE%, and Y% to ensure that the amount of ATV loaded into the fibers reflected the success of the electrospinning process. The results in Table 4 show that as the amount of polymer in the fiber formulations increased, the DL% decreased. This aligns with previous research on ornidazole electrospinning fibers, where an increase in the PVP amount decreased the DL% (Tort et al. 2019). Moreover, all formulations demonstrated high EE%, which aligns with the results reported by Reda study (Reda et al. 2017) and can be attributed to the polymeric solution that solidified during electrospinning, effectively capturing the drug within the polymer fiber matrix. As a result, the likelihood of drug loss during this process was minimal. The high Y% can also be attributed to the use of optimal conditions during fiber production, resulting in minimal drug loss.

The disintegration test application on fibers correlated directly with polymer quantity in Group 1 (F1, F2, and F3). In Group 3 (F7 and F8), the disintegration time, as shown in Table 4, was faster at 3 minutes with the higher ethanol volume in F8 compared to the lower ethanol volume in F7, which took 3.2 minutes. This could be interpreted as ethanol evaporation during the electrospinning process, resulting in porous fibers that facilitated more water permeation, thereby assisting in disintegration. This was not observed with other formulations containing co-solvents, such as Tween 80, PG, and glycerin, in which the disintegration depended on the type of co-solvent, as the amount of PVP was constant. The time of complete disintegration for all electrospun fibers was comparable to the 3-minute disintegration time, which was similar to that of sildenafil electrospun fibers produced from PVA and PVP (Torres-Martínez et al. 2020).

The *in vitro* release for all tested electrospun fibers revealed that F3 achieved better release due to its higher PVP content than the other two formulations. This agrees with findings from a previous study by the Alshaya group (Alshaya et al. 2022), who prepared ATV–nifedipine nanofibers and observed faster release due to PVP, a hydrophilic polymer that hastened dissolution of the fibrous mat and, consequently, the release of the loaded drugs. Additionally, electrospun fibers formulated with PG were identified as the most effective co-solvent, exhibiting a higher release within 30 minutes due to the high miscibility of PG with water, which led to rapid dissolution of fibers accompanied by ATV. In F8, the increased volume of ethanol in the formulation resulted in a less viscous solution, which led to the formation of nanosized fibers with a high surface area, approaching rapid fiber hydration. This may have assisted in the release of ATV.

The relationship between disintegration time and *in vitro* release of the fibers demonstrated an inverse correlation for Group 1 (F1–F3). This effect can be attributed to the higher polymer content, which necessitated larger volumes of the disintegration medium, thereby promoting additional hydrogen bonding and facilitating drug release. The release profiles of Group 2 (F4–F6) and Group 3 (F7–F8) were primarily influenced by the type of co-solvent and the volume of ethanol, respectively.

To probe fiber morphology and measure fiber diameter, SEM examination was conducted for the three selected formulations, F3, F5, and F8, as illustrated in Fig. 4. The selection of F3, F5, and F8 was based on their faster release behavior in each formulation group. Fig. 4A shows that these formulations produced smooth-surfaced fibers without visible crystals on the surface, indicating a positive interaction and even distribution of ATV and polymers. However, beads were formed within the fibers of the F8 sample when the polymer concentration decreased due to the increasing ethanol volume. This may have been due to the electrospinning process, which is likely the reason for bead formation. This result aligns with the study by Reda group (Reda et al. 2017), which demonstrated that increasing polymer concentration decreases the number and size of beads. Further, the decrease in polymer concentration produced fibers with smaller diameters, i.e., nanosized (Garg and Bowlin 2011).

Additionally, the lower viscosity of electrospinning formulations led to the formation of nanosized fibers ranging from 134.9 to 821.9 nm in F3 and F8. In contrast, F5, the more viscous formulation, exhibited fiber diameters ranging from 1.050 to 1.630 μm , with only a few fibers displaying nanosized characteristics. Gatti coworkers found a direct correlation between polymer concentration and fiber diameter using polyethylene oxide (Gatti et al. 2013). Zeng study also demonstrated that the solubility and compatibility of the drug within the drug–polymer–solvent system were crucial factors influencing fiber morphology (Zeng et al. 2003).

As shown in Fig. 4B, all images displayed fibers with different magnifications, demonstrating successful formulation. This suggests that ATV and the polymers were soluble in ethanol and compatible and that homogeneous fibers could be fabricated without any phase separation.

According to the above results, the F8 fiber formulation was chosen for tablet batch preparation since it had nanosized diameters, a faster disintegration time than other formulations, and achieved 93.9% release of ATV within 30 minutes.

The four unidirectional buccal tablet batches (B1, B2, B3, B4) passed weight variation, thickness, hardness, surface pH, and disintegration tests, as presented in Table 5. Their weight variation corresponded to 7.5%, which, according to the USP, was acceptable, as was tablet hardness. The tablet thickness was 3.33–3.46 mm \pm 0.005–0.015, close to results for aceclofenac buccal tablets (Koirala et al. 2021).

The surface pH ranged from 6.4 to 6.9, similar to the surface pH of aceclofenac buccal tablets and to normal salivary pH (Koirala et al. 2021).

The adhesion of the buccal tablet to the mucosa is a crucial property. B1 exhibited higher mucoadhesive strength due to its higher HPMC content compared to the other three formulations. B3, which contained a higher amount of sodium alginate, also showed good adhesive value. These results suggest that adhesive strength was sufficient to keep the tablet in place at the buccal site for the entire treatment period, comparable to the mucoadhesive strength reported in previous work on hydralazine mucoadhesive tablets prepared from mixed polymers of sodium carboxymethylcellulose, Carbopol 934, and microcrystalline cellulose (Samanthula et al. 2022). To conclude, all buccal tablet formulations exhibited suitable mucoadhesive properties.

For tablet disintegration, the addition of sodium alginate (SA) and croscarmellose sodium (CCS) helped improve disintegration times in B2, B3, and B4. B2, which contained 50 mg of SA and 10 mg of CCS, had a faster disintegration time than B3, which included a higher SA content of 60 mg and 10 mg of CCS. The increased SA in B3 may have formed a more viscous layer upon hydration, slowing down disintegration. B4 had the fastest disintegration time, possibly due to its lower amounts of both SA and CCS.

Furthermore, swelling is a property of polymers that initiates drug release. B1 showed an SI of 103% (Fig. 5B) due to a higher amount of HPMC, which increased water uptake and resulted in proportionally greater swelling (Matharu et al. 2011). B2, B3, and B4 contained HPMC and sodium alginate, which showed higher SI due to the presence of two polymers.

According to Table 2, which screened the contents of four batches with a total weight of 200 mg, each batch contained fixed elements that were not altered and variable contents, as the contents mainly depended on the release rate of ATV, which was preferred not to be prolonged, considering tablet residence within the mouth and patient compliance. The materials were unchangeable; first, the ethyl cellulose, which equals 50 mg, represented the outer layer of the tablets that covered the core from three directions. The other fixed materials were the electrospun fibers loaded with ATV and Mg stearate as a lubricant.

The *in vitro* dissolution study outcome, as presented in Fig. 5C, for the first batch, B1, consisted of HPMC K4M, mannitol, and microcrystalline cellulose, serving as a mucoadhesive material, diluent, and binder, respectively (Thoorens et al. 2014; Salehi and Boddohi 2017; Liu et al. 2023). The release rate (presented in Fig. 5C) was very retarded, reaching 25% within 4 hours. It was believed that the B1 contents should be modified to enhance ATV dissolution; thus, mannitol was replaced with lactose, as a previous study found that lactose, compared to mannitol, improved the dissolution of griseofulvin (Umeh et al. 2013).

Additionally, the binder was changed to sodium alginate, starting with 50 mg, as it has mucoadhesive properties (Kesavan et al. 2010). This led to decreasing the HPMC K4M to 10 mg in the hope of keeping the mucoadhesive strength. The new addition to the tablet batches was croscarmellose sodium, a super-disintegrant that increases disintegration, thereby enhancing dissolution. This formulation, B2, enhanced ATV dissolution, achieving 83.27%

within 4 hours, while maintaining a very close value of mucoadhesive strength to formulation B1. Additionally, the time of disintegration decreased from 54 to 43 minutes.

Another trial was B3, by increasing the sodium alginate to 60 mg and keeping the croscarmellose sodium constant (10 mg). The dissolution rate decreased to 70.27%, and the time of disintegration increased to 52 minutes. The non-improved B3 outcomes led to the formulation of the last batch, B4, with a lower amount of both the super-disintegrant (7.5 mg), which potentiated the release of ATV, and the sodium alginate (15 mg), resulting in ATV dissolution reaching 100% within 3 hours and disintegration occurring at 42 minutes, with good mucoadhesive properties.

The *in vitro* dissolution study was followed by *ex vivo* permeation, and the outcome was harmonized with the permeation through sheep mucosa in another study, which formulated ATV as nano-electrospun fibers but as a buccal mucoadhesive film, and the permeated ATV was around 60% (Alshaya et al. 2022). Another study found that the permeation of ATV from buccal batches after 24 hours was approximately 50% (Abu-Rumman et al. 2022). These studies affirmed that ATV permeates through the buccal cavity, and B4 achieved a comparable ATV permeation amount.

The flux of ATV through sheep mucosa reached 1.34 mg/cm²/hr, surpassing the 0.82 mg/cm²/hr (same surface area) reported in a different study (Abu-Rumman et al. 2022); however, their study utilized a cellulose membrane, which does not replicate the unique properties of animal mucosa.

Conclusion

The study goals were achieved by formulating a unidirectional buccal tablet loaded with electrospun fibers of ATV after the approval of several studies. Additionally, ATV dissolution was approximately 100% after 3 hours in the B4 buccal unidirectional tablet formulation, aided by the super-disintegrant croscarmellose sodium, which indicated a decrease in residence time within the buccal cavity and thereby improved patient comfort.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

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Author contributions

Zainab Muaiz was responsible for experimental work, writing, discussion, data analysis, and gathering. Masar Mohamed's role involved supervision of the work, writing, and data analysis.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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